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METHODOLOGY FOR ASSESSING ROCKFALL SUSCEPTIBILITY WITHIN THE AMBIT OF CIVIL PROTECTION: THE SAFETY PRO- JECT.

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The mission of the SAFETY European project is to provide to Civil Protection Authorities (CPA's) the capability of periodically evaluating and assessing the potential impact of geohazards on prone sites, and specifically rockfalls. We present the methodology applied in a strategic road (GC-200) located in Gran Canaria (Canary Islands, Spain). We have exploited STONE [1], a GIS based rockfall simulation software which computes 2D and 3D rockfall trajectories starting from the identification of the sources areas and maps of the dynamic rolling friction coefficient and of the normal and tangential energy restitution coefficients. The appropriate identification of these parameters determines the accuracy of the simulation. We have developed a method to calibrate and validate STONE in a volcanic context for the first time, to provide to the Canarian CPA a reliable tool to assess hazard posed by rockfall at regional scale, which could be later applied in any island of the archipelago.

Keywords: Rockfall modelling, Methodology, Civil Protection, Canary Islands

INTRODUCTION

Geohazards are contemplated in the Spanish legislation in the Basic Civil Protection Regulation (1992) which establish the drafting of territorial emergency plans for each Autonomous Community. The Basic Regulations also establish the possibility of producing special plans focusing

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on particularly significant hazards in each region. These special plans are an important development, since they must necessarily involve in-depth knowledge and characterization of geohazards prior to the operational structure in the emergency state, and have to base on quite thorough scientific research. Due to the volcanic origin of the Canary Islands, the authorities approved in 2010 the Special Emergency Plan for Volcanic Hazards that provides an inventory of means and resources, and lays down action protocols to apply in the case that a volcanic event comes true, including other related geohazards. Rockfalls in the Canary Islands are very common and they represent a major threat to society, costing lives, disrupting infrastructures and destroying livelihoods. During the volcanic crisis in El Hierro (2011) numerous rockfalls were triggered, affecting the road network of the island and causing a great social alarm. The SAFETY European project aims to develop accurate tools to provide to Civil Protection Authorities (CPA's) the capability of periodically evaluating and assessing the potential impact of rockfalls. In the present work, we show the procedure carried out in a strategic road located in Gran Canaria (GC-200) by applying STONE rockfall modeling.

DESCRIPTION OF THE TEST SITE

The Canary Islands is a populated outermost Spanish region and one of the most popular touristic destinations in Europe. The steep topography and geological complexity of the archipelago, influences the activation of intense slope dynamics and many slope failures occur. Rockfalls are the most frequent and damaging landslide type in the Canary Islands, producing damages on built-up areas and communication networks. Taking into account the priorities indicated by the CPA of Canaries, a pilot area was selected in the western extreme of the island of Gran Canaria. It is the GC-200 road, located between the localities of Agaete and Aldea (Fig. 1). The GC-200 road constitutes the main transportation corridor between both localities. With a length of 34 km, the road path is very tortuous following the contour of the coast, a very step coastline with the highest cliffs in Europe (Risco Faneque, 1027 m a.s.l.). From the point of view of mobility, the GC-200 is a strategic road with a heavy traffic estimated at 1500 vehicles per day. The geology of the test-site area is within the domain of the basaltic shield stage, Middle Miocene in age. Along the road, an alternance of alkaline basaltic deposits and pyroclastic flows can be observed. Both materials can be the rockfall sources. The road is frequently cut off by rockfalls and numerous boulders invade the road every month (Fig.1).

Fig. 1 The GC- 200 road between the localities of Agaete and Aldea. It is considered one of the most hazardous roads in Europe. Numerous rockfalls cut the road off every year.

METHODOLOGY

This work develops a methodology to provide to civil protection authorities the capability of evaluating and assessing rockfall hazard. The methodology is based on rockfall simulations, and involves three main phases: (1) inventory, (2) simulation, and (3) validation.

In the first stage, we have recorded the information and observations carried out by the Canarian CPAs about rockfall events occurred from January 2010 to March 2016, along the first 15 km of the GC-200 road. A total of 7811 rockfall events were reported. Based on this, a rockfall inventory map was developed defining accurately the location of each impact on the road. The information for each event includes wide data, such as kilometer point (PK), number of events, date, boulder size, etc. In parallel, we generated a database including all information available for each rockfall and we have also design and unified tab to be used by CPAs to collect future rockfall events data.

The goal of the simulation stage is the rockfall modeling at regional scale. Rockfalls are difficult to model with accuracy because it is necessary to determine precisely factors such as: the location of the source area, the size and shape of the boulder, the parameters of the bedrock, etc. [3]. To assess rockfall susceptibility in the test site, STONE was applied. It is a physically based software capable of modelling rockfall processes in three dimensions (3D), and of providing the potential rockfall trajectories [1]. The software requires the following input data: the location of the source areas, a digital elevation model (DEM), the starting velocity, and the coefficients of normal and tangential energy restitution and friction to simulate the loss of energy when rolling and at impact points. DEM was generated by the National Geographic Institute at a 5m x 5m resolution (www.ign.es). All the cells with slopes above 40° were considered as the sources areas, and five rocks for each cell were launched. In addition, we have compared some LiDAR point clouds, taken from different time-periods, to identify the areas with material losses to adjust better the source areas. According to the field observations and the geological map available -GEODE from IGME (www.igme.es)- four lithological units were differentiated and their coefficients were firstly obtained from the literature [4] [5] and then, they were calibrated with some well-known rockfall events occurred in the Canary Islands. The starting velocity in the preliminary simulation is null, but we will carry out new simulations considering different starting velocities for potential seismic scenarios. The software computes, for each DEM cell, the cumulative count of rockfall trajectories, the maximum computed velocity, and the largest flying height produced.

The third stage consists on validation, that is, to determine the accuracy of the developed simulations. The validation consists on quantifying the matching/mismatching between the rockfall inventory map and the simulated rockfall map. The analysis was applied considering the 7811 rockfall events documented in the road during the last 6 years, and calculating the percentage of computed rockfall trajectories that cross the rockfall inventory areas, as well as the percentage of the rockfall inventoried areas within the simulated outputs (Fig. 2).

RESULTS AND CONCLUSION

This study presents a methodology to provide to the Civil Protection Authorities of the Canary Islands the capability of evaluating and assessing rockfall susceptibility. The comparison of the map of the potential rockfall trajectories obtained by STONE with the well-known location of the impact points of the historical rockfalls along the road during the last 6 years, confirmed a

preliminary spatial representation for the potential extent of rockfalls along the GC-200 road. This map provides the percentage of trajectories that cross each cell. In the study area the highest density of trajectories is located in between the PKs 7 and 9 km, where high densities of rockfall events were identified (Zone A). Additionally, between the PKs 9 and 11 km high densities were also observed (Zone B). Overall, the numbers of trajectories are in agreement with the information and observations carried out by the Canarian CPAs (Fig. 2).

The validation stage makes evident that the travel paths and the depositional areas are successfully ascertained through numerical modelling. Results show success in 73.33% of the largest rockfalls inventoried (11 events).

We have calibrated and validated the STONE software [1] for the first time in a volcanic context, developing a reliable tool, which can be applied in any rockfall prone area of the archipelago.

Fig. 2 Comparison between the rockfalls identified in 2012 and the simulated rockfall map

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